

NOTES

Studies and Characterisation of the Heteropoly Ammonium Hexavanadomolybdate Dodecahydrate

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A new heteropoly complex salt $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoV}_6\text{O}_{19}] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$ has been synthesised and characterised by chemical and instrumental methods. The molecular weight of the heteropoly salt has been determined by determining cell dimension values by its X-ray powder diffraction studies. The powder file, with all the relevant data is furnished. The thermal depolymerization studies have been carried out and the compound is found to be stable at $520 \pm 10^\circ$.

A few heteropoly vanadates have been reported¹. But with the possible exception of 12-vanadophosphate anion², none of them has been well characterised nor their constitutions have been elucidated. The existence of isopoly anion $[\text{V}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{-8}$ has been distinctly confirmed in solution phase³. Considering the previous reports⁴, detailed investigation is reported here for the solid state isolation, characterisation and thermal stability measurements of an interacted complex of molybdenum with $[\text{V}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{-8}$ anion.

Experimental

pH and thermometric titrimetric techniques⁵, as discussed earlier⁴, have been adopted to establish the conditions of formation of the heteropoly compound. Aqueous solutions of .2M ammonium metavanadate (NH_4VO_3) and .05M molybdic acid were found to be workable. When .05M molybdic acid was gradually added to 40 ml of .2M NH_4VO_3 solution, there was a gradual increase in pH upto the addition of 55 ml of molybdic acid. It was followed by a plateau of constant pH 5.3 upto 65 ml of molybdic acid. Thermometric titrations⁵ corroborated the above results.

By comparing the results of pH and thermometric titrations from the graphs⁴, the range in volume of the reactants could be studied. Hence 65 ml of .05M molybdic acid was slowly added to 40 ml of .2M NH_4VO_3 solution at 5° to 10° with constant stirring. The whole reaction mixture was kept at low temperature for three hours and then

digested at a controlled temperature of 60° in a thermostat for six to eight hours till the volume reduced to half of its original. The mixture was then left for crystallization. After an interval of twelve days very small fibrous silky golden yellow crystals were collected which were further recrystallized from hot water. The complete analysis of the compound was done by chemical and instrumental methods. For estimation of molybdenum it was first separated⁶ from vanadium (as it interferes) by precipitating molybdenum quantitatively as MoS_3 by passing a continuous flow of H_2S to the compound solution, mixed with 5 ml of formic acid at 0. The solution was filtered, the precipitate containing MoS_3 was dissolved in minimum amount of concentrated HCl and a pinch of potassium perchlorate and then molybdenum was estimated as molybdenum oxinate⁷. Due to the above treatment V(V) is reduced⁷ to V(IV), imparting a deep blue colouration to the filtrate. So vanadium was directly estimated from the solution by titrating it against .02(N) KMnO_4 . The analytical values were corroborated by colorimetric determinations of molybdenum and vanadium by potassium thiocyanate and hydrogen peroxide methods⁸ respectively. Nitrogen and hydrogen were estimated by element estimation technique. (Found: Mo, 9.992; V, 3.451; N, 1.412; H, 3.318 per cent. Calcd. for $(\text{NH}_4)_2[\text{MoV}_6\text{O}_{19}] \cdot 12\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Mo, 10.104; V, 31.936; N, 1.450; H, 3.340 per cent).

For assigning the molecular formula, from the above percentage composition data, the existence of complex anion $[\text{V}_6\text{O}_{19}]^{-8}$ was taken into consideration⁹.

X-ray Powder Difference Studies :

Repeated attempts to isolate a sharp single crystal of the compound failed and so the X-ray powder diffraction technique⁹ was applied for the determination of cell dimensions and consequently the molecular weight of the compound. The results of the powder photograph of the compound have been entered in the form of a standard powder file in the following table.

Analysing the above powder file, the system was found to be orthorhombic with $a=9.62 \pm 0.02$, $b=16.25 \pm 0.02$, $c=6.24 \text{ \AA}$ and $\alpha=\beta=\gamma=90^\circ$. So the volume V per unit cell was calculated to be 975.468 \AA^3 . The space group was uniquely established as $D_{2h}^2\text{-P}_{\text{non}}$ from the following systematic presence of reflections: $hkl = \text{no condition}$; $0k1 = k+1$

d 1/1	9.0 100	11.0 30	12.70 27	12.70 27	(NH ₄) ₂ [MoV ₆ O ₁₉] 12H ₂ O Ammonium vanadomolybdate
Ra	CuK _α		λ=1.5405		dÅ
Filter—Ni					1/1
1/1 visual strip measurement					hk1
Ref. Nil					dÅ
					1/1
					hk1
System orthorhombic					12.7
a=9.62, b=16.25, c=6.24 Å					27
α=β=γ=90°					30
					15
					111
					3.10
					26
					600
					152
					610
					319
					040
					182
					620
					444
					582
					392
					440,402
					422
					622,623
					521
					630
					533
					621
					191
					250
					042

=2n; h0l=1+h=2n; hk1=h+k=2n; hoo=(h=2n); oko=(k=2n); col=(l=2n) and hk1=h+k+l=2n. The last condition gives the number of molecules in unit cell Z=2. The observed density ρ_{obs}=3.240 gm l⁻¹ against the calculated density ρ_{cal}=3.259 gm l⁻¹. From the relation $\rho_{obs} = \frac{1.66M.Z}{V}$, the molecular weight 'M'

of the compound came to 951.9 against the theoretical value 957.65.

Thermal Depolymerization Studies :

The thermal depolymerization of the compound has been studied in the light of the investigations made by West and Audrieth¹⁰ on a few heteropoly molybdates and tungstates. No reports on thermal depolymerization of heteropoly vanadates have been found in the chemical literature. The dissociation of the compound was observed at 130° when two molecules of water were eliminated which was confirmed by successive estimations. At 210° further two molecules of water along with two ammonia molecules were lost. The rest of the eight water molecules remained intact in the crystal lattice till 280°, above which they were completely removed. This work agreed closely with the work of Seroggie and Clark¹¹ on a few heteropoly salts. When the temperature was raised still higher, nearly at 520±10°, the compound was broken as a whole into the basic units of lower oxides of vanadium and molybdenum, which were confirmed by analysis. So the thermal stability of the compound is 520±10°.

Discussion

The generally accepted principle that condensation of heteropoly acids and salts depend upon

hydrogen in concentration has further been corroborated as the complex anion of vanadomolybdate appearing within pH 5.3. X-ray powder diffraction studies helped to find out the molecular weight from which it has been possible to conclude that the compound is monomeric. The thermal depolymerization studies reveal four phase degradation leading to the end basic units of V₂O₅ and MoO₃. It is difficult to predict some idea about the configuration of (NH₄)₂ [MoV₆O₁₉] 12H₂O as [V₆O₁₉]⁻⁸ isopoly unit is a new entity and yet deserves exhaustive X-ray studies for its structure determination. Vanadium's presence in different variable oxidation states and due to its possibility of appearance in the form of irregular VO₄ or bipyramidal VO₅, it is not possible at present to predict anything regarding the structural arrangement of this compound.

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Synthesis of Some New Heteropoly Salts

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IN this communication three distinctly new heteropoly salts of molybdenum, vanadium and tungsten with 1:6, central:condensing atom ratio are reported.

The conditions of formations are the same as has been discussed in the previous communications^{1,2}. The pH were maintained rigorously throughout the experiment.

6-Sodium tungstomanganate :

50 ml of .2M sodium tungstate, 45 ml of 0.05M manganese sulphate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together (pH 3.64), stirred vigorously for one hour, kept in a steam bath for three hours and left for crystallisation. Greyish white powdery compound was collected after an interval of seven days. The compound was analysed chemically and colorimetrically : (Found : Mn, 2.21 ; W, 48.23 ; Na, 1.00 ; H 2.25 ; calcd. for Na₁₀[MnW₆O₂₄]28H₂O : Mn, 2.41 ; W, 48.48 ; Na, 1.10 ; H, 2.45 per cent).

6-Ammonium molybdochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of 0.05M ammonium molybdate, 40 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 20 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed together rapidly at pH 2.8, digested for three hours, evaporated to crystallisation on a water bath and left overnight ; orange coloured flaky powdery compound was separated after an interval of five days. From analysis : (Found : Cr, 4.02 ; Mo, 46.72 ; N, 6.62 ; H, 3.32 ; calcd. for : (NH₄)₆ [CrMo₆O₂₄] 10H₂O : Cr, 4.22 ; Mo, 46.90 ; N, 6.68 ; H, 3.58 ; per cent).

6-Potassium vanadochromate :

Solutions of 50 ml of .013M ammonium metavanadate, 43 ml of .05M potassium dichromate and 14 ml of glacial acetic acid were mixed by constant stirring (pH 2.4) for half an hour, digested for two hours and crystallised on a steam bath. After an interval of ten days brick-red shining crystals were collected from analysis : (Found : Cr, 5.22 ; V, 31.83 ; K, 8.03 ; H, 2.31 ; calcd. for K₃[CrV₆O₁₉]12H₂O : Cr, 5.43 ; V, 32.00 ; K, 8.15 ; H, 2.51 per cent).

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Mixed Ligand Complexes of Some Bipositive Cations with 6-Mercaptopurine and Thioguanine in Solution

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6-MERCAPTOPURINE (MCP) and 2-amino-6-mercaptapurine (thioguanine, TGN) have been introduced in human cancer therapy, and has proved effective as anticancer agent in comparison to other purine derivatives like adenine and TGN. MCP and TGN having similar structures, form chelates with metal ions, which probably determine their activities.

The present communication deals with attempts to study mixed complexes of MCP and TGN with Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and Zn(II), using 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) or 2,2'-bipyridine (bipy) as primary ligands. Studies with Cu(II) and Zn(II) were not possible.

Chelating reactions between the above metal ions and MCP have been described by Freiser *et al*¹, while TGN complexes with Be(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Pb(II), UO₂(VI), Ca(II) and Mg(II) have been reported earlier². Formation constants of the mixed complexes have been determined using a modified form of Irving-Rossotti titration technique^{3,4}.

Experimental

All materials used were of reagent grade. Stock solutions (0.01M) of phen and bipy were prepared in water. 0.01M solutions of MCP and TGN were freshly prepared by dissolving in 0.02M alkali. Solutions of metal nitrates were prepared and standardized against EDTA⁵.

pH measurements were done using an Elico pH meter (model LI-10) with glass (EK-62A) and calomel electrodes. The pH meter was calibrated with 0.05M potassium hydrogen phthalate solution.

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